

Attitude towards Adoption of Technology and Constraints Faced by Dairy Farmers in Punjab

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This study aims to analyze attitudes towards adoption of technology and constraints faced by dairy farmers. Primary data was collected through pre-structured and pre-tested questionnaires. One-sample t-test and factor analysis were used for the analysis of the data. A total of 100 dairy farmers were selected from two districts of Punjab, namely Ludhiana and Bathinda, conveniently. The results of the study revealed that artificial insemination techniques used by dairy farmers at the farm in consultation with a veterinarian (3.87). They believe that technologies reduce operational cost in dairy (3.74) and they used a milking machine at the farm (3.73). However, they have not adopted technology for feed storage and mobile application and software for dairy management (2.68). Lack of skilled labour availability (4.05) and lack of awareness about various modern technologies (3.84) were reported as important constraints in the adoption of technology.

Keywords: Dairy farmers, technology adoption, constraints

Value chains played a limited role in facilitating the adoption of new technologies in dairy farms in India (Janssen & Swinnen, 2019). Attitude towards dairy farming and market orientation of farmers had a positive and significant relationship with their knowledge about breeding and feeding practices (Sharma et al., 2016). Dairy husbandry training plays a crucial role in promoting the adoption of improved dairy technologies, which in turn leads to significant enhancements in milk production and income for smallholder farmers (Getachew et al., 2020). Due to a lack of awareness, finance, and technical guidance, the training programs were found to be highly beneficial in updating farmers' knowledge and practices (Chander et al., 2020). Small-scale farmers would be absorbed in value chains and would eventually improve productivity and sustainability in the dairy sector (Burkitbayeva et al., 2020). Small farmers had a low level of information source utilization, whereas large farmers had a medium level of utilization (Singh et al., 2022). Despite the potential of the dairy sector, its contribution is limited due to traditional practices and underinvestment (Khalid, 2022). Issues such as inadequate cold chain facilities, inefficient transportation, and a lack of standardized quality control measures at various stages contribute to potential losses and quality degradation (Prakash, 2022). Major barriers involved high land costs, limited credit access, poor extension networks, and insufficient fodder availability (Khalid et al., 2022). Kumar et al. (2022) concluded that fostering desirable changes in the entrepreneurial behaviour of dairy farmers necessitates addressing the economic, infrastructural, technical, socio-psychological, and marketing related constraints

they perceive in the study area. The success of the apps developed by the veterinary university highlights the potential of localized, context-specific digital solutions in driving positive change at the farm level (Burkitbayeva et al., 2020). Kaushik et al. (2023) studied the impact of technology and innovation on agribusiness is evident globally, with precision dairy farming technologies offering significant advantages such as cost optimization, enhanced quality control, waste reduction, economies of scale, efficient resource utilization, improved productivity, standardized processes, enhanced decision support, and overall farm management. There is a need for improved access to finance, market information, and risk management strategies (Balakrishnan et al., 2024). The most crucial ones among them were inadequate support by the government machinery, a complete lack of dairy-related education, and huge cost factors for the adoption of technology (Kaushik et al., 2024). The importance of addressing constraints like lack of financial independence and decision-making autonomy faced by women farmers to enhance adoption and build resilience against climate change impacts (Reddy et al., 2024). Addressing challenges of dairy is crucial for fostering a competitive, sustainable, and adaptable dairy industry in the context of the changing agricultural landscape (Kumar et al., 2024). Somtiya et al., (2024) revealed that more than half (55.67 per cent) of the respondents had a medium scientific orientation, the majority (61.08 per cent) had medium economic motivation and a higher share (45.81 per cent) had a high level of knowledge about scientific dairy farming practices. Sharma et al. (2020) concluded that depending on the feeding management, there was a difference in the milk yield obtained. Singh et al. (2015) concluded by emphasizing the urgent need for government-level policies to address challenges in dairy and support the adoption of dairy farming as a viable entrepreneurial venture. In this context, this study aims to analyze attitudes of dairy farmers towards the adoption of technology and constraints faced by them.

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Method

Participants

A descriptive research design was adopted to achieve the objectives

of the study. The population of the study consists of farmers of the Ludhiana and Bathinda districts of Punjab. Primary data were collected. A total of 100 dairy farmers comprising 50 from each district, were selected through a random sampling method.

Measure

Primary data were collected using a well-structured, pre-tested interview schedule. Likert scale-based questions were used in the questionnaires with responses ranging from strongly agree (5) to strongly disagree (1).

Statistical Analysis

The data collected through the questionnaire were organized and analyzed using Microsoft Excel and SPSS software. Various

statistical tools like mean frequency percentage, one sample t-test and factor analysis were employed to derive meaningful insights from the data.

Procedure

The schedule was designed based on insights from previous literature reviews and information relevant to the adoption of technology and constraints faced by dairy farmers. The questionnaire included sections on demographics (age, educational qualification, number of family members), farm characteristics (herd size), technology adoption and constraints (financial, technical, & infrastructural challenges). A pilot study was conducted with five respondents to test the validity and reliability of the questionnaire.

Table 1

List of Items Included in Questionnaire

Items	Author(s)
I use milking machines in my dairy farm	Researcher
I have adopted advanced feed storage and mixing techniques	Researcher
Artificial insemination techniques adopted at farm	Researcher
I use mobile applications or software to manage dairy operations	Researcher
To what extent do you believe that technological advancements have reduced operational costs in your dairy business	Researcher
I frequently consult veterinarians for animal health and productivity enhancement	Researcher
My farm uses renewable energy sources like biogas	Researcher
I have received training in modern dairy farming practices	Anonymous (2021)
Constraints in adoption of technology	
High initial investment costs prevent me from adopting new technology	Khalid et al (2022)
Lack of access to financial support or loans limits my ability to adopt technology	Chander et al (2020)
Lack of awareness about modern dairy technologies is a major barrier	Bhattu (2016)
Poor infrastructure for transportation and storage affects technology adoption	Kaushik et al (2024)
Inadequate veterinary services are a challenge in dairy farming	Anonymous (2017)
The fluctuating prices of milk reduce my motivation to invest in new technology	Rathore (2023)
Shortage of skilled labor prevents me from utilizing modern technology effectively	Researcher
Lack of knowledge about various mobile applications related to scientific dairy farming practices	Brar et al (2020)
I face challenges in understanding the technical requirements of modern dairy technologies	Researcher
Fear of technology failure stops me from adopting modern practices	Researcher

Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile of Respondents

This section interprets demographic profile of respondents, such as gender, age, family type, education level, occupation, family size, monthly income, and dairy farming experience.

Table 2

Demographic Profile of Respondents (n=100)

Particular	Category	Frequency	Per cent
Gender	Male	98	98
	Female	2	2
Age (years)	Below 25	2	2
	25-30	7	7
	36-50	68	68
	Above 50	23	23
Qualification	Primary education	24	24
	Secondary education	48	48

Occupation	Undergraduate	26	26
	Post graduate	2	2
	Retired	17	17
Family type	Private employee	54	54
	Homemaker	29	29
	Nuclear	53	53
Monthly income (in Rs)	Joint	47	47
	35000-60000	15	15
	60000 - 100000	37	37
Experience in dairy farming	Above 100000	48	48
	Less than 5 years	19	19.0
	5-10 years	27	27.0
Size of dairy farm	11-20 years	42	42.0
	More than 20 years	12	12.0
	Less than 5	1.0	1.0
	5- 10	11	11.0
	11-20	45	45.0
	More than 20	43	43.0

Note. (Primary data)

Table 2 reveals majority 98 per cent respondents were male followed by 2 per cent who were female. Majority 68 per cent were between 36-50 years old finding in line with Shivagangavva (2022) followed by 23 per cent were above 50 years old. Majority 48 per cent respondents had education up to secondary education followed by 26 per cent were had education up to undergraduate level. Majority of respondents 54 per cent had agriculture as their primary occupation followed by 29 per cent were private employees. Majority 53 percent had a nuclear family followed by 47 per cent had a joint family. Majority of the respondents 53 per cent had monthly income 10-30 thousand followed by 48 per cent had 31-50 thousand. Majority of respondents 42 per cent had 11-20 years dairy farming experience followed by 27 per cent had 5-10 years dairy farming experience. Majority 45 per cent had 11-20 animals in their dairy farm followed by 43 per cent had more than 20 animals.

Table 4

Extent of Adoption of Technology by Dairy Farmers (n=100)

Statements	Mean	SD	t	p
I adopted Artificial Insemination technique at my farm	3.97	1.14	8.43	<0.001
I frequently consult veterinarians for animal health and productivity enhancement	3.87	1.06	8.20	<0.001
You believe that technological advancements have reduced operational costs in your dairy business	3.74	1.08	6.80	<0.001
I use milking machines in my dairy farm	3.73	1.20	6.05	<0.001
I have received training in modern dairy farming practices	3.28	1.46	1.91	0.05
My farm uses renewable energy sources like biogas for energy needs	3.08	1.46	0.54	0.58
I have adopted advanced feed storage and mixing techniques	2.90	1.31	-0.76	0.44
I use mobile applications or software to manage dairy operations	2.68	1.33	-2.38	0.02

Note. (Primary data) (Mid-point of scale, i.e., $\mu=3$) Significant at 5% level of significance

Table 4 represents extent of adoption of technology. The respondents were asked their agreement and disagreement on 5 point scale denoted (5) strongly agree and (1) strongly disagree. One sample t-test was applied and mean value of all the statement have been compared with mid value of scale ($\mu=3$). Highest mean score corresponded to the statement I adopted Artificial Insemination

Table 3

Marketing Channels (n=100)

Types of channel	Frequency	Per cent
Cooperative societies	31	31.0
Private dairies	26	26.0
Local market	41	41.0
Direct to consumers	2.0	2.0
Total	100	100

Note. (Primary data)

Table 3 shows that local markets were the most common sales channels (41 per cent), followed by cooperative societies (31 per cent), private dairies (26 per cent), and direct sales to consumers (2 per cent). This demonstrates the dominance of local and cooperative systems in milk marketing and the relatively limited use of direct-to-consumer models finding in line with (Dass et al., 2022).

technique used on my farm (3.97), followed by I frequently consult veterinarians for animal health and productivity enhancement (3.87). The least mean score corresponded to the statement I have adopted advanced feed storage and mixing techniques (2.90), and I use mobile applications or software to manage dairy operations (2.68) finding in line with finding of (Brar et al., 2020).

Table 5

Constraints Faced by Farmers in Adoption of Technology (n=100)

Statements	Mean	SD	t	p
Shortage of skilled labor is reported constraint for utilizing modern technology effectively	4.05	0.95	10.96	<.001
Lack of awareness about modern dairy technologies is a major barrier	3.84	1.25	6.70	<.001
Fear of technology failure stops me from adopting modern practices	3.83	1.22	6.78	<.001
High initial investment costs prevent me from adopting new technology	3.79	1.15	6.82	<.001
The fluctuating prices of milk reduce my motivation to invest in new technology	3.78	1.06	7.29	<.001
Limited access to technical support makes it difficult to implement new technologies	3.72	1.23	5.80	<.001
Inadequate veterinary services are a challenge in dairy farming	3.65	1.24	5.23	<.001
Lack of access to financial support or loans limits my ability to adopt technology	3.62	1.11	5.55	<.001
Poor infrastructure for transportation and storage affects technology adoption	3.60	1.13	5.27	<.001
I face challenges in understanding the technical requirements of new dairy technologies	3.57	1.35	4.22	<.001

Note. (Primary data) (Mid-point of scale i.e. $\mu=3$) Significant at 5% level of significance

Table 5 reveals the results of the one-sample t-test conducted on various constraint-related statements reveal that dairy farmers face various challenges in adopting technologies. All statements yielded mean scores significantly higher than the neutral value of 3.0, with p-values ≤ 0.05 , indicating that these constraints are strongly perceived and widely experienced by the respondents.

The statement high initial investment costs prevent me from adopting new technology (Khalid et al., 2022) corresponded (mean = 3.79) and it is found to be significant (t-value = 6.82) with ($p < .001$). This result clearly reflects the financial constraints perceived by dairy farmers as a major constraint in adopting technological. Similarly, Lack of access to financial support or loans limits my ability to adopt technology (Chander et al., 2020; Kaushik et al., 2024) also showed a significant (mean = 3.62), indicating that the unavailability of credit or institutional finance serves as a critical impediment to innovation at the farm level.

Another significant challenge identified was the lack of awareness about modern dairy technologies (mean = 3.84) and (t-value = 6.704), again confirming that information asymmetry and

limited exposure to technical knowledge are major barriers. Additionally, respondents reported that poor infrastructure for transportation and storage affects technology adoption (mean = 3.60, $p < .001$).

Veterinary support was also a matter of concern, as the statement inadequate veterinary services are a challenge in dairy farming (mean = 3.65). This suggests that animal healthcare services are insufficient or difficult to access, which adversely affects farmers' confidence in implementing new animal management technologies. Furthermore, the market related issue was highlighted through the statement that the fluctuating prices of milk reduce my motivation to invest in new technology, which had (mean = 3.78), reinforcing the fact that economic instability weakens investment intent.

Factor Analysis

The KMO value was found to be 0.63, Bartlett's Test of Sphericity, Chi-Square value was found to be 132.93 and value was significant (p -value $< .001$).

Table 6

Factor Analysis

Factor	Factor name	% of variance	Items	Item loading
1	Financial and Economic Barriers	24.93	High initial investment costs prevent me from adopting new technology	0.46
			Lack of access to financial support or loans limits my ability to adopt technology	0.75
			The fluctuating prices of milk reduce my motivation to invest in new technology	0.70
2	Knowledge and Technical Constraints	15.40	Lack of awareness about modern dairy technologies is a major barrier	0.64
			I face challenges in understanding the technical requirements of modern dairy technologies	0.61
			Fear of technology failure stops me from adopting modern practices	0.71
			Limited access to technical support makes it difficult to implement new technologies	0.66
3	Infrastructure and Resource limitations	11.15	Poor infrastructure for transportation and storage affects technology adoption	0.65
			Inadequate veterinary services are a challenge in dairy farming	0.67
			Shortage of skilled labor prevents me from utilizing new technology effectively	0.75

Table 6 revealed factor analysis revealed three major factors that collectively explain the challenges faced by dairy farmers in adopting modern technology. These factors account for a total variance of 51.49 per cent

Financial and Economic Barriers: This factor explains 24.93 percent variation in the original data set. High initial investment costs prevent me from adopting new technology, lack of access to financial support (Khalid et al., 2022) or loans limits my ability to adopt technology, and fluctuating prices of milk reduce my motivation to invest in new technology loaded with this factor.

Knowledge and Technical Constraints: This factor explains 15.40 percent variation in the original data set. Lack of awareness about modern dairy technologies is a major barrier, fear of technology failure stops me from adopting modern practices, and limited access to technical support makes it difficult to implement new technologies loaded with this factor.

Infrastructure and Resource Limitations: This factor explains 11.15 percent variation in the original data set. This factor, loaded with three items, poor infrastructure for transportation and storage affects technology adoption (finding in support of finding of (Kaushik et al., 2024). Inadequate veterinary services are a challenge in dairy

farming and shortage of skilled labor prevents me from utilizing new technology effectively.

Conclusion

This study analyzes farmers' attitudes toward adoption of technology and constraint faced by dairy farmers. Majority dairy farmers sell milk in the local market. Dairy farmers used Artificial Insemination technique at their farm with veterinarian's consultation. Dairy farmers perceived that adoption of technology reduces the operation costs in the dairy. Higher initial investment, lack of knowledge and infrastructure were reported as important constraints. These important constraint extracted i.e. financial and economic barriers, knowledge and technical constraints, infrastructure and resource limitations in adoption of technology by dairy farmers. Addressing these constraints helps in boosting dairy farming in the state.

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